

Advanced Transport Management System (aTraMS) using On-Board Diagnostics

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Abstract

On-Board Diagnostics or OBD diagnostic device communicates with the car and reads the diagnostic information from the car. It is a computer-based system built into modern passenger cars that monitor emission-related controls and the performance of the engine and detects malfunctions. This device is installed in a power train control module (PCM), which is generally a combined control unit, consisting of the engine control unit (ECU) and the transmission control unit (TCU). It provides some useful data to the user. The problem with the present device is that, to support different applications, it uses separate modules and till today it is seen only in high-end vehicles. The existing product is a processor-based application; hence it uses external RAM and ROM.

The proposed system is microcontroller-based, which provides all in one support like Ethernet, USB, GPS, Bluetooth (using UART), Wi-Fi (using SPI), LTE, 6 axis sensor support, Cloud support, Front panel IO, Multi-range voltage (up to 48V) on a single chip. It also supports an Android application through which we can easily gather information about the vehicles through smartphones. The system is integrated with LTE wireless network and cloud computing technologies. It can perform real-time vehicle status surveillance. The monitored features cover engine rpm, vehicle speed, airbags, active suspension, ABS (Anti Braking System), Gear, light, air conditioning, coolant temperature, fault codes, and other vehicles dynamic information.

The vehicle information will be transmitted to the cloud server via a wireless network for fault analysis. Once the cloud server detects fault conditions, the proposed system could classify the fault conditions depending on vehicle type and its model year. Then the cloud server will report the fault code analysis results to the user and describe the repair procedure. The proposed system will greatly shorten the time to detect vehicle trouble conditions. The system presented in this research work has a very high value in the applications of vehicle

maintenance and fleet management. The complete designing process will be done using ALTIUM designer 17.0

Keywords: OBD, MIMXRT1021CAG4A, ALTIUM designer 17.0, power train control module

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 On-Board Diagnostics

OBD stands for “On-Board Diagnostics.” The OBD is a computer-based device, which was generally designed to minimize emissions by monitoring the performance of major engine components. In the beginning days, 1st Generation of OBD was discovered and developed throughout the 1980s. These early systems use proprietary connectors, hardware interfaces, and protocols. The OBD-I was largely unsuccessful because the reporting of emissions-specific diagnostic information was not standardized. OBD-II is an improvement over OBD-I in both capability and standardization. OBD-II has first introduced in the year 1994 and became a requirement for all cars and light trucks. This 2nd-generation OBD discovers and diagnoses problems that occurred in the vehicle systems and subsystems with the data reported by the ECUs [1]. It gives DTCs that have been generated by the computer system while malfunctioning occurred in the vehicle as well as gives the real-time status of the systems according to sensors output which is connected to different systems of the vehicle. The OBD-II has a pin in the connector that provides approximately 12Volt power for the scan tool from the vehicle battery, which eliminates the need of connecting a scan tool to a power source separately. This OBD-II came in two models OBD-II_A and OBD-II_B.

An OBD system consists of a central system, a chain of sensors, a connection point, and an indicator creating a complete monitoring system. The OBD system consists of Electronic Control Unit or an ECU. The ECU acquires input from different types of sensors throughout the vehicle. The ECU uses this data to either control parts of the vehicle, like fuel injectors, or monitor for issues. Modern vehicles consist of more than 100 sensors to keep everything running the way. These sensors cover every area from the engine and chassis to the electronic system itself. Each one of these systems sends codes to the ECU, specifying the source and the parameters of the signal. After receiving the information, the ECU “reads” and interprets this signal. If a sensor sends information to the ECU that falls outside of the normal range, the ECU saves the information as a code called a Diagnostic Trouble Code, or DTC. The OBD-II Diagnostic Trouble Codes are 4- digit, preceded by a letter: P for engine and transmission (power train), B for body, C for chassis, and U for the network. These letters indicate the source and nature of the problem[2]. DTC codes are usually standardized but maybe manufacturer-specific. When a DTC is saved, the ECU sends a signal to the indicator light to state that a problem has been found. The DTC can also be pulled by linking a sensor to the connector for the OBD system.

The different types of DTC codes are collected by ECU, Further, and these signals were transferred to the vehicle dashboard to turn on the appropriate indicator lights. These lights, known formally as Malfunction Indicator Lights or MILs. The MIL provides an early

warning system for vehicle malfunctions. For example, if the light turns on and stays on, the problem is minor. If the light flashes, the problem is urgent. All of the data and DTC codes collected by the ECU can be accessed via the Diagnostic Link Connector or DLC. The DLC is the point of access for vehicles with OBD systems and is often found beneath the dashboard on the driver's side of the vehicle, though it may be located elsewhere in commercial vehicles. Current vehicles are made with a standard OBD-II system so that any scan tool with a type 2 cable can connect to the type 2 connector.

1.2 OBD-II aTraMS

Advanced Transport Management System or aTraMS will empower us to track, monitor, and manage vehicles anytime, anywhere. The solution addresses various issues faced by customers including high operational costs, vehicle downtime, tracking, job scheduling, monitoring driver performance, vehicle maintenance planning, high repair costs, and safety issues such as vehicle theft, breakdown, and emergency services for accidents. The developing system can collect the data from the vehicles and has the capability to rectify the problems that are occurred. For example, if an owner has given his vehicle for rent and wants to know the status of the vehicle like location, Travel history, ECU condition, speed, etc., he can access it through his mobile. **In this paper only few components are explained. i.MXRT Schematics, Memory Interface Schematics, Connectivity Schematics, USB Schematics will be explained in the next research paper.**

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Hu Jie, et.al [1] proposed a method of Developing PC-Based Automobile Diagnostic System Based on OBD. According to vehicle testing, the entire hardware system is reliable and stable. The diagnostic software is easy and intelligent, and the entire system can run smoothly and diagnose accurately. Compared to hand-held diagnostic devices, this diagnostic can run faster and have more powerful repairing help and guidance. Since the device is wired, the extraction of data from different ranges is not possible to meet the stricter emission regulations and higher requirements of economy, power, safety, and comfort, the application of electronic control technology is the inevitable trend of development of the automobile industry. The wide application of electronic control technology makes the structure of automotive electronic control systems more and more complicated. It is more difficult to find the cause and position of the fault. Data in vehicle technical supports shows that the time for finding fault is 70%, while the time for troubleshooting and maintenance accounts for 30%. Given this situation, the corresponding fault diagnosis system is added in the development process of the Electronic Control Unit (ECU), to achieve the on-board diagnostics and off-line diagnostics. An automotive fault diagnosis system is used with the OBD system so that the off-line fault diagnostics can be achieved. In essence, it is equivalent to the terminal equipment of an onboard self-diagnostic system, playing the role of human-computer interaction.

Shi-Huang Chen et.al [2] proposed Vehicle Fuel Pump Service Life Evaluation Using On-Board Diagnostic (OBD) Data. This paper proposed a vehicle fuel pump early warning system using OBD data. The proposed system makes use of vehicle speed as well as revolutions per minute (rpm) of the engine to calculate the fuel pump runtime parameters. Then one can determine the remained lifetime of the fuel pump and give an early warning indicator to the user when its remained lifetime is to be close to zero. The proposed system can only measure faults related to engine and diagnoses it but multiple application is not

present. The modern EFI gasoline engine has the following components. They are engine control unit (ECU), fuel injector, fuel pump, fuel pressure regulator, wiring harness, and various sensors, including crank/cam position sensor, manifold absolute pressure (MAP) sensor, exhaust gas oxygen sensor, coolant temperature sensor, throttle position sensor, etc. The EFI systems have electromechanically operated injectors opening for a predetermined length of time called the injector pulse width. The pulse width is determined by the engine's engine control unit (ECU) and depends on the information from various engine sensors. The fuel is delivered from the tank through a filter, and a regulator controls its operating pressure. The fuel is delivered to the engine in precise quantities and is injected into the inlet manifold as the inlet valve opens and is drawn into the combustion chamber by the incoming air.

Reza Malekian et.al [3] proposed a Wireless OBD II Fleet Management System. The testing of the communication between the OBD II reader and the emulator verified that the system could inter-continued wireless communication and GPS location tracking. The delay resulting from the initializations of the system could be reduced to improve the efficiency of the system. The effect of the delay introduced by initializations means that the car can only be driven once all initializations are done, to avoid loss of initial parameter measurements. New techniques to reduce this delay need to be developed. OBD II readers have mostly been utilized for diagnostic purposes: identifying and reporting specific vehicle faults. With the advent of various mobile technologies, wireless communication, and the global positioning system (GPS), the use of OBD II readers for real-time tracking and monitoring has gained popularity, especially in the area of fleet management. Fleet management is the total management of a company's fleet of vehicles, covering every aspect of the life cycle of a vehicle from procurement to disposal. It is thus important for companies to employ efficient fleet management systems to reduce risks, increase the quality of service and improve the operational efficiency of a fleet at a minimal cost. Fleet management also encompasses the analysis of the impact of transportation on the environment. It was reported in that approximately 27 % of the total carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions were a result of the combustion of fuels from vehicles. Vehicle emissions are influenced by driving style and vehicle parameters such as acceleration, speed, distance travelled, and fuel consumption. Speed and distance information in fleet management can be utilized for assessing driver behaviour on the road, prevent accidents, and improved road safety. Fleet management systems can also avail us with a fuel consumption monitoring capability, which can result in reducing running costs and environmental pollution.

2.1 General Problem Formulation

The problem with the present device is that, to support different applications, it uses separate modules and till today it is seen only in high-end vehicles. Hence to rectify the problem faced or in the view of upgrading the existing system, the research work focuses on developing a controller-based system. The developed system can collect the data from the vehicles and can rectify the problems that are occurred. For example, if an owner has given his vehicle for rent and wants to know the status of the vehicle like location, Travel history, ECU condition, speed, etc., he can access it through his mobile.

2.2 Problem statement

2.2.1 First method

OBD System has changed significantly over the years since its introduction in the 1980s. Originally, the system would notify the user that there was a problem using the MIL but would not store any information as to the nature of the problem. In modern days, as cars became more advanced, the number of sensors installed in vehicles expanded, as did the amount of information stored inside the system. The first OBD systems were proprietary in nature, so they differed between manufacturers. Before 1990, the codes, systems, and information gathered by each OBD system varied widely from manufacturer to manufacturer. While these systems proved useful, they were unnecessarily complex for technicians to work with. The technicians had to purchase a new tool and cable for every vehicle make or had to invest in a scanner that had an array of adapter cables for multiple vehicle makes. Due to the proprietary nature of these systems, users were often forced to go to dealership technicians to diagnose issues[3].

2.2.2 Second method

The OBD-II system is widely used in vehicle workshops, service dealers also in cars nowadays. Due to the operation of OBD is quite difficult, the general drivers or owners cannot access the OBD data easily if the car is not with them. The existing device cannot acquire the real-time vehicle location accurately. The speed and performance of the CAN bus is low in a car for accessing the data from the OBD-II socket. The present devices communicate with smart phones by using only a Bluetooth module to access the information stored in the OBD-II board. The existing products which are using now are manually operated. The devices like Blue drive and ELM327 can withstand up to 12V only. If the battery transmits more voltage than 12V, it may cause damage to OBD-II Scanner. The processing speed of these devices is low, if there is any fault that occurs in a car we get to know it after few minutes. The existing devices are not secured [4]

To overcome the above mentioned problem statements, the research work focuses on

- Implementation of On-Board-Diagnostics to achieve real time data from the vehicle.
- The data storing and accessing through the cloud and absolute position accuracy.
- Multi range voltage support up to 48V.

Summary

In the expanding world of IOT, the OBD port remains important to vehicle health, safety, and sustainability. Although the number and variety of connected devices for vehicles increases, not all devices report and track the same information. Additionally, compatibility and security can vary among devices. With the multitude of OBD protocols, not all telematics solutions

are designed to work with all vehicle types that exist today. Good telematics solutions should be able to understand and translate a comprehensive set of vehicle diagnostic code [6]

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Block Diagram of aTraMS

The main microcontroller is NXP's MIMXRT1021CAG4A. All other components are interfaced with this microcontroller as shown in fig.1. SDRAM is interfaced with i.MXRT1020 microcontroller. It has 16 Bit data lines and is used to transfer data to store in a memory and SPI flash memory is also included. Micro SD memory card connector is interfaced to store the data externally. For example, If the car met with an accident and there is a lot of damage, then by removing the SD card and hand it over to the technician to verify the data and check where the damage has occurred. Wi-Fi and Bluetooth with antenna modules are interfaced to upload the data to the cloud and to establish wireless connectivity over a long distance. RTC controller is a real-time clock controller, which is used to keep the time for the microcontroller. For that real-time clock, we are provided a coin cell battery. For the programming purpose micro-USB is connected to USB to UART IC. 6-Axis Sensor is interfaced to the microcontroller which is composed of a 3- axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope. RS232/RS485 Transceiver is interfaced to allow reliable data transmission from transmitter to receiver by using a DB9 connector. DB9 is the 9-Pin connector. The boot mode switch is used for booting purposes. 4G Mini PCIe is used to upload the information to the cloud. This 4G Mini PCIe requires one USB signal this is given through the USB MUX. In the vehicle, OBD-II connector is used. From this OBD-II connector, CAN-H and CAN-L signal are taken from the CAN Transceiver and is given to the microcontroller, then ethernet is used for high-speed connectivity. This OBD-II will give 12V Supply. This is given to the Power regulator. For optional connectivity power jack is also connected[5]

Fig 1 : Block Diagram of aTraMS

3.2 Power Consumption Report

The power requirement for each component is referred from the datasheet and included as shown in Fig.2. Hence at the end, total input power requirement and output power are calculated. This also shows the buck and voltage regulator selection and their power requirements.

Major Power Components			Component's Power Requirement					Board Power & Budget						
Part description	Manufacturer Part Number	Number of Components Used	Pin name	Operating Voltage			Current Consumption(mA)	Power(W)	VCC_12	VCC_5V	VDD_SMS_IN	VCC_3V3	VCC_1V8	Power of individual Component (W)
				Min	Typ	Max								
MX RT1020	MIMINT0021CAF4A	1	DCDC_IN	3.00	3.30	3.60	80.00	0.26				80.00		1.75479
			VDD_HIGH_IN	3.00	3.30	3.60	50.00	0.17				50.00		
			VDD_SVMS_IN	2.40	3.30	3.60	0.25	0.00			0.25			
			USB_OTG1_VBUS	4.40	5.00	5.50	25.00	0.13		25				
			VDD4_ADC_SPS	3.00	3.30	3.60	40.00	0.13				40.00		
			WACC_SDO	3.00	3.30	3.60	100.00	0.33				100.00		
			WACC_GPI0	3.00	3.30	3.60	135.00	0.45				135.00		
SDRAM	IS42S161604-6T U	1	VDD	3.00	3.30	3.60	140.00	0.46				140.00		0.594
			VDDQ	3.00	3.30	3.60	10.00	0.03				10.00		
Micro SD Card Conn		1	VCC	2.70	3.30	3.60	200.00	0.66				200.00		0.792
SPI_FLASH	IS25LP064A	1	VCC	2.70	3.30	3.60	25.00	0.08				25.00		0.099
CAN IC	MCP2562FD-E/SN	1	VDD	4.50	5.00	5.50	70.00	0.35		70				0.42396
			VIO	1.80	3.30	5.50	1.00	0.00				1.00		
Ethernet IC	KSZ8021PNB	1	VDDA	3.14	3.30	3.47	34.00	0.11				34.00		0.18216
			VDDIO	3.14	3.30	3.47	12.00	0.04				12.00		
LTE MODULE	EC25_Mini_PCIE	1	VCC	3.00	3.30	3.60	2700.00	8.91				2700.00		10.692
WiFi-Bluetooth	A7WLC3000	1	VBAT	1.50	3.30	4.20	281.00	0.93					281.00	1.207404
			VDDIO	3.00	3.30	3.60	23.90	0.08				23.90		
6-Axis Sensor	MPU6050	1	VDD	2.35	3.30	3.45	3.90	0.01					3.90	0.411444
			VLOGIC	1.71	3.30	3.30	100.00	0.33				100.00		
RS32/RS485 Transceiver	MAX3160EAP-T	1	VCC	3.00	3.30	5.50	6.00	0.02				6.00		0.02376
Total (mA)								0.00	95.00	0.25	3837.90	103.90	16.181	
Power Fails								VCC_12	VCC_5V	VDD_SMS_IN	VCC_3V3	VCC_1V8		
Finalized Regulator Part number									TP554560B-Q1	TP57A24330BVR	TP554560B-Q1	TP57A24330BVR		
DC/DC Converter Type									Buck Regulator	LDO	Buck Regulator	LDO		
Maximum output current (A)								22	5	0.3	5	0.3		
DC/DC Converter Output Voltage Min (V)								11.4	4.75	3.135	3.135	1.71		
DC/DC Converter Output Voltage Max (V)								12.6	5.25	3.465	3.465	1.89		
Output Voltage of DC/DC Converter Vio (V)								12	5	3.3	3.3	1.8		
Input Voltage of DC/DC Converter - Vi (V)									12	5	5	5		
Efficiency of DC/DC Converter - η									0.870	0.660	0.950	0.360		
Required Output Current of DC/DC Converter - Io (A)								1.587	3.314	0.000	4.605	0.125		
Input Current of DC/DC Converter - Ii (A)									1.587	0.000	3.200	0.125		
Power Dissipation of DC/DC Converter - Pd									2.476	0.001	0.800	0.399	3.276	
Total Power Required for the System Operation (W)													13.457	

Fig 2 : Power Consumption Report

3.3 Power Tree

Power tree includes the power requirement for every pin of the components as shown in fig.3. Initially, the total power required is to be drawn from an OBD port or a power supply, later the input supply is given to the regulator part, and the required output is taken. The output of the regulators is distributed based on the requirement for each component.

Fig.3 : Power Tree

3.4 OBD2 Connector and Power Schematics

3.4.1 OBD2 Connector

The OBD2 connector is usually located under the dashboard, beneath the steering wheel column. It is a 16-Pin Connector. There are 5 protocols in the OBD2 Port, and a car will normally only use one of them.

1. J1850 PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) - Used by Ford Motor Company and Mazda.
2. J1850 VPW (Variable Width Modulation) - Used by General Motors and in light trucks.
3. ISO9141-2 - Older protocol in Chrysler, European, and Asian vehicles 2000-2004.
4. ISO14230-4 KWP2000 - Commonly used in cars from 2003.
5. ISO 15765-4 CAN-BUS - First introduced in 2004 then mandatory after 4 years.

In this research, ISO 15765-4 CAN-BUS is used for gathering information from OBD2 Port. As shown in fig.4, Pin 16 of the connector provides a battery voltage of 12V. C1 and C2 are the two high pass and low pass capacitors. This voltage is named as VCC_OBD and is connected to the input side of the main power filter circuit. Pin 6 and Pin 14 are FLEXCAN2_CANH and FLEXCAN2_CANL. These signals are the differential signals which are interfaced with the CAN transceiver IC. Pins 3, 11, 12, 13 are Ethernet differential

signals connected to Ethernet PHY IC. These 4 pins are interfaced with 0-ohm resistors because the 0-ohm resistor act as jumpers and they can be more easily removed than jumper wires. Pin number 1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 10, 15 remains Not Connected (NC).

Fig.4 : OBD2 Connector

3.4.2 Main Power

The main power supply filter circuit schematic is shown in fig.5. The purpose of power supply filters is to smooth out the ripple contained in the pulses of DC obtained from the vehicle's OBD port or a battery while increasing the average output voltage or current. The circuit consists of a 12V, 2A PTC (positive temperature coefficient) fuse in order to control the input power supply. It consists of an on-board switch in order to turn on and turn off the power supply to the circuit. It consists of some passive elements like common mode chokes, ferrite beads, LC as a further filtering element in order to obtain a proper output response. The common-mode (CM) choke, where two coils are wound on a single core, is useful for suppression of electromagnetic interference (EMI) and radio frequency interference (RFI) from power supply lines and the prevention of malfunctioning of power electronics devices. From the main power, the output is given to the buck regulator to obtain the required power for further process.

Fig.5 : Main power

3.4.3 48 to 5V Buck Converter

TPS54560BQDDA1 is the buck regulator from the Texas instruments. Few of the circuits require a 5V supply as an input in the schematics. Hence in order to provide a supply, a 48 - 5V buck regulator is used as shown in fig.6. It has some advantages like it accepts a large input range up to 60v and it can synchronize the input with the switching frequency by adjusting the resistor connected to RT/CLK. By using a fly back diode reverse flow can be avoided and 10uH is used to avoid variation in the current at the output. It contains two comparators inside it depends upon the feedback from the output it will change its comparator value. Maintain 0.8V feedback to the FB pin it can be enabled or disabled by using Enable pin (EN). The voltage divider circuit is connected to enable the pin in such a way that whenever it receives the voltage greater than or equal to 1.2V, it turns on the regulator, else it will be in off condition.

Fig.6 : 48 to 5V Buck Converter

3.4.4 5V to 3.3V Buck regulator

TPS54560BQDDAQ1 is the buck regulator from the TI Company and the research work using this because more components require 3.3V power supply. It has some advantages like it accepts a large input range up to 60V, it can synchronize the input with the switching frequency by adjusting the resistor connected to RT/CLK. By using a fly back diode reverse flow can be avoided and 10uH is used to avoid variation in the current at the output. It contains two comparators inside it depends upon the feedback from the output it will change its comparator value. In this work 0.8V feedback is maintained to the FB pin it can be enabled or disabled by using Enable pin EN. To enable or disable another reset IC TC1270ALVRCTR is used, it is an active low IC. There are three ways to enable or disable the buck regulator by using Reset IC. 1) By using interrupt pin from MCU, 2) By using Push Button, 3) By using the software or using GPIO (watchdog timer).

Fig.7 : 5V to 3.3V Buck Converter

3.4.5 5V to 3V3 LDO – SNVS

LDO stands for Low Drop out, can operate at a low potential difference between input and output. It is sometimes referred to as a low-loss or saturation type linear regulator. To provide SNVS voltage for the MIMXRT1021CAG4A microcontroller internal circuit this 5V to 3V3 LDO is used. The input for this LDO is from a 48 to 5V buck regulator. Input Capacitor (C_{in}) is used to improve source impedance, noise, or PSRR. Output Capacitor (C_{out}) is used to improve load transient, noise, or PSRR. Here the research work recommended $C_{in} = 1\mu\text{F}$ and

$C_{out}=2.2\mu F$. The output voltage is decided by the FB pin resistors. So, to get a required constant output need to calculate the FB resistance R1 and R2. For 3.3V output voltage, the recommended R1 and R2 values are $R1= 52.3K$ and $R2 = 30.1K$. $R1|| R2 = 19K$ ohms for best accuracy.

Output Voltage Calculation:

$$V_{out} = \frac{R1+R2}{R2} \times 1.204$$

Consider,

$$R1= 52.3K \text{ and } R2 = 30.1K \text{ then}$$

$$V_{out} = \frac{52.3k+30.1k}{30.1k} \times 1.204$$

$$V_{out} = 3.296 \text{ nearly equal to } 3.3V$$

Fig.8 : 5V to 3.3V LDO – SNVS

4. Components placement in PCB

We choose 70*70 diameter PCB where we placed our component by referring to some videos. We divided the PCB into several areas like power, front panel IO, RF Etc. The main microcontroller is placed in the middle because it connected to all the components initially, components like SDRAM, Flash, and SD card are placed near to the microcontroller to avoid data loss then voltage supplies are made into one group and placed right to the microcontroller front panel IOs are RS232/485, USB jack, RJ connector are placed left to the microcontroller then RF signal related components are placed on top of the PCB other components like coin batteries, boot switch and connectors are placed on the bottom of the PCB because those are more immune to noise

Fig. 9 : Top view of PCB

Fig.10 : Bottom view of PCB

4.1 PCB Stackup

The PCB stackup is the substrate upon which all design components are assembled. PCB boards are made up of 2,4....20 layer based on application. We have selected 2-layer PCB for our board, it contains a solder mask to prevent metallic contact, silkscreen(top overlay) for component reference naming, dielectric to separate layers, top layer for signals and power routing, and bottom layer for Ground plane we referred NXP website for Copper thickness. We have chosen FR4 as a dielectric material top and bottom layers are 1.4mil solder mask thickness on each side is 0.4mil

Fig.11 : 2 Layer PCB Stackup

Layer Name	Type	Material	Thickness (mil)	Dielectric Material	Dielectric Constant	Pullback (mil)	Orientation
Top Overlay	Overlay						
Top Solder	Solder Mask/...	Surface Mat...	0.4	Solder Resist	3.5		
L1	Signal	Copper	1.4				Top
Dielectric 1	Dielectric	None	56	FR-4	4.8		
L2	Signal	Copper	1.4				Bottom
Bottom Solder	Solder Mask/...	Surface Mat...	0.4	Solder Resist	3.5		
Bottom Over...	Overlay						

Fig.12 : Different layers of PCB

4.2 Routing of PCB

The connections are made using copper routings. The trace width of the copper routings varies based on the amount of current needed. For example, if the current required is more than 300mA then the polygon layer has to be poured on the PCB.

Fig.13 : Top view of PCB Routing

Fig.14 : Bottom view of PCB Routing

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1 48V to 5V Buck regulator circuit design

Fig.15 : 48V to 5V Buck Regulator

- Buck regulator input voltage Buck= 7V to 48V
- regulator input current Buck= 2A to 2.5A
- regulator output voltage = 5V
- Buck regulator output current = 4A

5.2 5V to 3.3V Buck regulator circuit design

Fig.16 : 5V to 3.3V Buck Regulator

- Buck regulator input voltage Buck= 5V
- Regulator input current Buck= 2A
- Regulator output voltage = 3.3V
- Buck regulator output current = 5A

48V to 5V Buck regulator circuit output waveform and its responses as shown in the **Fig.17**

Fig.17 : Input-Output Current and Voltage Waveform

The table below are recorded results observed during the simulation implementation of the buck regulator circuit. The input voltage is set between 7V – 48V, 2A – 2.5A for the buck regulator circuit. Whenever the enable pin receives the input voltage of 1.2V the circuit goes to turn-on mode. The output of the buck regulator circuit is 5V, 4A. Whenever the input voltage falls below 7V, the input at the enable pin falls below 1.2V. Hence buck regulator goes to turn-off mode.

Table 1 : 48V to 5V Input Transient

Input Transient						
Sim ID	Vout Maximum	Vout Minimum	Overshoot Settle Time	Undershoot Settle Time	Overshoot	Undershoot
9 to 3	5.14 V	4.85 V	0.08 ms	0.08 ms	0.14 V	0.15 V

Table 2 : 48V to 5V Output Transient

Load Transient						
Sim ID	Vout (Max)	Vout (Min)	Overshoot Settle Time	Undershoot Settle Time	Overshoot	Undershoot
11	5.07 V	4.93 V	0.17 ms	0.17 ms	0.07 V	0.07 V
2	5.08 V	4.91 V	0.17 ms	0.18 ms	0.08 V	0.09 V

5V to 3.3V Buck Regulator circuit output waveform and its responses are shown in the Fig.18

Fig.18 : 5V to 3.3V Input-Output Current and Voltage Waveform

The table below are recorded results observed during the simulation implementation of the buck regulator circuit. The input voltage is set between 5V, 2A for the buck regulator circuit. Whenever the enable pin receives the input voltage of 1.2V the circuit goes to turn-on mode. The output of the buck regulator circuit is 3.3V, 5A. Whenever the input voltage falls below 7V, the input at the enable pin falls below 1.2V. Hence buck regulator goes to turn-off mode.

Table 3: 5V to 3.3V Input Transient

Input Transient						
Sim ID	Vout Maximum	Vout Minimum	Overshoot Settle Time	Undershoot Settle Time	Overshoot	Undershoot
3	3.40 V	3.19 V	0.50 ms	0.12 ms	0.10 V	0.10 V

Table 4 : 5V to 3.3V Input Transient

Load Transient		
Sim ID	Vout Maximum	Vout Minimum
5	3.36 V	3.22 V
4	3.36 V	3.22 V
2	3.36 V	3.22 V

CONCLUSION

The research work implemented a platform called “Advanced Transport Management system” for driver monitoring and vehicle diagnostics which integrates OBD-II, android, and backend processing technologies such as complex event processing that may include vehicle subsystem monitoring. The system is capable of identifying reckless driving habits and vehicle subsystems like air conditioning system, airbag monitoring, engine system, and many more, which is a major advantage for travel and transportation authorities. The system is also capable of detecting possible sensor failures earlier and alerts the driver via the mobile phone which saves the cost of fuel and maintenance due to running the vehicle with a poor performance for a long time. The Android application support is given to access the data from the cloud platform which is available as a free download in Google Play Store. The proposed system uses an NXP based MCU which is able to provide real-time alerts to the user.

On-Board Diagnostic is one of the computer systems equipped in cars that can discover and diagnose problems that occurred in vehicle systems and subsystems with the data reported by the ECUs. OBD-II gives DTCs that have been generated by the computer system while malfunctioning occurred in the vehicle as well as gives the real-time status of the systems according to sensors output which is connected to different systems of the vehicle. It empowers us to track, monitor, and manage vehicles anytime, anywhere. The solution addresses various issues faced by customers including high operational costs, vehicle downtime, tracking, job scheduling, monitoring driver performance, vehicle maintenance planning, high repair costs, safety issues such as vehicle theft, breakdown, and emergency services for accidents.

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